

EYE TRACKING STUDY OF PACKAGING FORM JUDGMENT

Gojko Vladić, Gordana Delić, Nemanja Kašiković, Stefan Đurđević,
Bojan Banjanin

Department of Graphic Engineering and Design, Faculty of Technical Sciences,
University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Scientific paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3416787
vladicg@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: *Eye tracking technology is used for design judgment in various industries. Packaging industry also utilizes this technology to gain insight in to consumer's perception of the packaging and to gain in-depth knowledge about interaction on the consumer-packaging relation. Packaging design can be divided in to two main sections: graphic design and the form design. So far majority of eye tracking research in the packaging field has been oriented towards exploring influences of the graphic design. This paper aims to present study conducted by eye tracking concentrated on influence of packaging form the consumer's judgment of the packaging characteristics. Results show relation between viewing times and judgment of the packaging according to specific characteristic.*

Key words: packaging, form, design judgment, eye tracking

1 INTRODUCTION

Creating a desirable image of a product, communicating trustworthiness to the customer, influencing identity of products and manufacturers brand, differentiating the product amongst competition and education of consumer are some of tasks packaging should tackle. All of these tasks can be achieved by original, innovative and unique packaging capable of encoding marketing statements. Introducing communicative value to the packaging through visual information, packaging language should lead observer to notice the product, decode the message, cause interest, make a decision about purchasing and remember it permanently (Silayoi et al., 2007).

Besides communication clarity packaging aesthetic and functionality influences consumer behavior and the perception of the products value. According to Reimann these attributes are especially important in the markets where all other consumer needs have already been satisfied (Reimann et al., 2010).

Packaging is one of most important marketing instruments, having in mind that majority of purchasing decisions are made at the point of sale. According to study conducted by Connolly and Davidson percentage decisions are made at the point of sale up to 73% (Connolly et al., 1996). Having this in mind packaging become ultimate selling tool through stimulating impulsive purchases. Consumers mainly perceive product attributes through the packaging, thus it significantly influences their product preferences and purchasing decisions. Besides all mentioned communication advantages, manufacturers are also able to reduce promotional costs through well conceptualized and designed packaging. Schoormans and Robben propose that in-store marketing is product itself, and packaging as an integral part of the product one of the main tools (Schoormans et al., 1997).

Packaging effectiveness is influenced by its elements. Elements of packaging design can be categorized in numerous ways, but main division is made between packaging form defining shape, size and ergonomics of the packaging and graphic design defining graphic elements such as pictures used, type and size of the font, placement of the graphic elements, amount of information, legibility, etc.

All aspects of packaging design as well as consumer behavior require adequate and constant attention from marketers, distributors and researchers. Graphic design of the packaging, its efficiency and influence is the most researched area of the packaging design. On the other hand packaging form is far less researched although the shape, size and ergonomics are also important elements influencing the packaging effectiveness. The shape of the packaging can strengthen natural brain's tendency for contact with the packaging and the higher level of stimulation is noted in case of ergonomic packaging. Furthermore, there is a proved connection between the constructional form, shape and perceived value and the acceptance level of the price of the wrapped product (Garber et al., 2009; Vladić et al., 2015).

In case of fast moving consumer goods such as food, drinks, hygiene products, etc. consumers attention is extremely limited. Hoyer suggests that the average purchase time taken for groceries is 8.5 seconds (Hoyer, 1984). Taking in to consideration that Hoyers study was conducted more than 30 years ago and since then number of similar product at the place of purchase has tripled, the

purchase decision time today is even shorter. Having in mind such a short time for observing a product and decision making, it is very important to gain insight in to that process. Eye tracking technology offers objective observation of the product scanning process. As already mentioned majority of the packaging design research is graphic design oriented, this is even more pronounced in the studies done using eye tracking technology.

2 THE SUBJECT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

Subject of the research is packaging shape and relation between viewing time and packaging characteristic's judgment. The packaging can be judged based on various criteria, such as suitability for intended use, functionality, aesthetics, ergonomics, etc. The main goal of the research was to determine is there a relation between of time spent observing certain packaging and judgment given to that packaging design based on its shape. In order to concentrate on the shape of the packaging all other design elements had to be removed. Examples of beverage packaging were chosen and rendered in to images used as stimuli without any graphic elements, color, etc. This makes the form of the packaging only influencing factor on observer's judgment. Stimuli shown to the participants are shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Stimuli used in the experiment a) Stimuli used for judgment of suitability of the packaging design and b) Stimuli used for judgment of aesthetics and ergonomic of the packaging design

Images were incorporated in the wider survey concerning the influence of the beverage type on the packaging shape (Delić et al., 2018).

While participants were answering the questions the eye tracking method has been used in order to follow their eye movement, simultaneously recording saccades and fixations. This method allows objective insight into the observer's real behavior, on which areas the sight is focused and which are omitted. This is much more useful than only recording subjective opinions, especially when observation time is of interest, having in mind that participants would not be able to report exact time of stimuli viewing.

The experiment was conducted in the controlled laboratory conditions. Eye tracking device used was GazePoint GP3, sampling frequency 60 Hz. Data gathering and results analysis was done using GazePoint Analysis 5.3.0 Professional Edition software. All stimuli were presented to the observers using the Eizo ColorEdge CG241W computer monitor. Observers were distanced 80 to 100 cm from the monitor screen, depending on their comfort and position needed for successful eye tracking process. Figure 2 shows equipment used and schematics of experimental setup.

Figure 2: a) Experimental setup b) Eye tracking device GazePoint GP3

Survey was completed by 30 participants, average age of participants was 22 years. Due to elimination of some participant's data caused by movement and disruption of eye tracking, 23 of participant's data sets were suitable for further analysis. Out of that 23 data sets, 8 random participant's data sets were chosen for further analysis. As there was no time restraints for answering the survey questions, each of the participants had different time line, this caused complexity of the eye tracking data analysis, resulting in relatively small sample. More than 200 areas of interest were produced in order to get insight in to viewing pattern of each stimuli by participants. Time of the viewing, number of fixations and returning views were analyzed, heat maps were produced in order to illustrate the attention of the observer given to each packaging. The video of fixations and saccades captured during survey was also analyzed in search for possible explanations of results.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the survey was conducted with simultaneous eye tracking, results were assembled in to matrix so the comparison could be made between viewing times of the packaging design which was judged as most suitable for the type of beverage stated in the survey and average viewing time of designs not chosen by the observer. Table 1 shows the time of the viewing, number of fixations and returning.

Table 1: Viewing time, no. fixations and returning views for judgment of packaging suitability for the beverage type

<i>Packaging selected as most suitable</i>						<i>Average of other packaging</i>			
<i>Packaging</i>	<i>User</i>	<i>Time viewed Sec.</i>	<i>Time %</i>	<i>Fixation No.</i>	<i>Revisit No.</i>	<i>Time viewed Sec.</i>	<i>Time %</i>	<i>Fixation No.</i>	<i>Revisit No.</i>
AOI 61	1	4.178	49%	8	5	1.54	18%	4.57	3.00
AOI 53	2	0.575	8%	1	0	0.37	5%	1.43	0.43
AOI 41	3	1.737	22%	7	5	0.29	4%	1.71	0.71
AOI 37	4	0.534	7%	3	2	0.24	3%	2.29	0.71
AOI 29	5	4.429	73%	14	10	1.75	25%	8.43	4.86
AOI 21	6	3.41	38%	11	10	1.56	18%	6.57	4.43
AOI 11	7	0.758	10%	3	3	0.55	7%	2.86	1.29
AOI 3	8	3.195	36%	10	4	0.90	10%	3.86	2.43
<i>Average:</i>		2.35	30%	7.13	4.88	0.90	12%	3.96	2.23

Data shows that viewing time of the packaging selected as most suitable is significantly longer than average time of viewing designs that were not chosen on the same criteria. It is important to note that in few cases designs that were not chosen as most suitable were viewed longest time. On further inspection, it seems that reason for that was last minute change of opinion. For example participant had chosen the design as most suitable and changed the answer at last moment before confirmation. In further studies it could be interesting to ask participants to make hierarchy of suitability and to compare those grades to the viewing times. Greater numbers of fixations and returning views can be explained by the fact that participants were comparing the design judged as most suitable with other designs, although not all participants had applied the same strategy while judging the designs.

Alongside numerical values presented in the table, heat maps of the observers gaze produced based on fixation data during the time of judging, which is the same as active time of area of interest used for collecting data. Heat map presenting the viewing pattern of one participant judging the suitability of the packaging for beverage type is shown in Figure 3. The most viewed areas are presented as warmer color. In this case the suitability for carbonated drink was judged and it is noticeable that some of the designs were judged based just on quick glance or even on the peripheral view.

Figure 3: Heat map of viewing pattern while judging suitability of packaging design for certain beverage type

Times of the viewing, number of fixations and returning views for the design judged as most aesthetic and average for all other designs are presented in Table 2. Similarly as in the case of viewing times of the previous criteria in case of aesthetic judgment the packaging design judged as most aesthetic was viewed the longest time and had the most fixations and revisits.

Table 2: Viewing time, no. fixations and returning views for judgment of packaging aesthetic

Packaging selected as most aesthetic						Average of other packaging			
Packaging	User	Time viewed Sec.	Time %	Fixation No.	Revisit No.	Time viewed Sec.	Time %	Fixation No.	Revisit No.
AOI 140	1	1.688	20%	7	4	0.75	9%	2.22	0.89
AOI 129	2	1.266	17%	5	1	0.22	3%	1.70	0.70
AOI 126	3	2.678	34%	10	4	0.48	6%	1.89	1.00
AOI 107	4	0.951	13%	4	4	0.21	3%	1.50	0.60
AOI 98	5	2.705	45%	8	5	0.43	7%	1.44	0.44
AOI 88	6	1.852	21%	8	4	0.825	9%	3.3	2
AOI 84	7	1.765	22%	6	4	1.07	14%	4.11	2.00
AOI 66	8	6.16	69%	19	13	1.62	18%	6.00	3.89
Average:		2.38	30%	8.38	4.88	0.70	9%	2.77	1.44

Heat map of the observers gaze produced from fixation data during the time of judging designs aesthetic is shown in Figure 4. Image shows that all of the designs were observed in order to make the decision, the differences in viewing pattern compared to previous criteria could be caused by the fact that aesthetic is more refined criteria than suitability and that caused more careful examination of the designs shown.

Figure 4: Heat map of viewing pattern while judging aesthetic of packaging design

Data for design judged as most ergonomic and average for all other designs are presented in Table 3. Again, viewing times of most aesthetic design are longest and had the most fixations and revisits. This is showing the trend that design which is best according certain criteria is most viewed and referenced for

comparison to other designs thus resulting in greater number of fixations and returning views.

Table 3: Viewing time, no. fixations and returning views for judgment of packaging ergonomic

Packaging selected as most ergonomic						Average of other packaging			
Packaging	User	Time viewed Sec.	Time %	Fixation No.	Revisit No.	Time viewed Sec.	Time %	Fixation No.	Revisit No.
AOI 220	1	2.814	33%	7	4	0.51	6%	2.00	0.89
AOI 214	2	0.698	6%	3	1	0.00	2%	0.4	0.20
AOI 204	3	2.771	35%	7	2	0.14	2%	0.78	0.22
AOI 190	4	2.172	30%	9	7	0.60	8%	3.57	2.00
AOI 180	5	2.447	40%	7	4	0.45	7%	2.33	1.22
AOI 170	6	1.205	14%	4	1	0.04	0%	0.67	0.11
AOI 162	7	0.279	4%	1	0	0.27	3%	1.60	1.00
AOI 150	8	3.539	39%	14	10	0.93	10%	4.89	3.56
Average:		1.95	25%	6.50	3.63	0.37	5%	1.98	1.13

Heat map of the observers gaze produced from fixation data during the time of judging designs ergonomics is shown in Figure 5. Similarly as in case of aesthetics judgment all of the designs were observed and each of the designs was examined carefully in order to make the decision which one is most ergonomic.

Figure 5: Heat map of viewing pattern while judging ergonomic of packaging design

4 CONCLUSION

The packaging form alongside graphic design is most important factor in forming consumer's opinion about the product contained in the packaging. By eliminating all the graphic design characteristics of the packaging participants in this study were directed to make the judgment about suitability, aesthetics and ergonomic of the packaging based solely on the packaging form. Eye tracking results show that the best design by all criteria category had longest viewing times, most fixations and revisiting views. This indicates that viewing time can be used for extracting conclusion about design quality. This claim should be further examined by more precise experiment introducing gradation in to judgment, and then comparing the viewing times and results of the judgment. The interesting fact that different judgment criteria produces different viewing patterns also should be further examined in future studies.

Acknowledgments: *The research is supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology Development of the Republic of Serbia, project number: 35027 "Development of software model for scientific and production improvement in graphic industry".*

5 REFERENCES

Connolly, A, Davidson, L (1996) How does design affect decisions at point of sale?, *Journal of Brand Management*, Vol. 4 no. 2, pp. 100-107.

Delić, G., Vladić, G., Banjanin, B., Vasić, J. (2018) The influence of the type of a beverage on its packaging shape, *Proceedings 9th International Symposium on Graphic Engineering and Design GRID 2018*, 8-10 November 2018, Novi Sad, pp. 243-252.

Garber, L., Hyat, E., Boyna, U. (2009) The effect of package shape on apparent volume: an exploratory study with implication for package design, *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, Vol.17 no. 3, pp. 215-234.

Hoyer, WD. (1984) An examination of consumer decision making for a common repeat purchase product", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 11, pp. 822-829.

Connolly, A., Davidson, L. (1996) How does design affect decisions at point of sale?,, *Journal of Brand Management*, Vol. 4 no. 2, pp. 100-107.

Schoormans, JPL, Robben, HSJ (1997) The effect of new package design on product attention, categorization and evaluation, *Journal of Economic Psychology*, Vol. 18. no. 2–3, pp. 271–287.

Silayoi, P., Speece, M., (2007) Importance of packaging attributes: a conjoint analysis approach, *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol.41 no.11–12, pp. 1495-1517.

Reimann, M, Zaichkowsky, J, Neuhaus, C, Benderd, T, Weber, B (2010) Aesthetic package design: A behavioral, neural, and psychological investigation, *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 20 no. 4, pp. 431–441.

Vladić, G., Kasiković, N., Dedijer, S., Stančić, M, Đurđević, S. (2015) Influence of packaging shape on a price presumption, *International Joint Conference on Environmental and Light Industry Technologies 19 – 20 November 2015 Budapest*.